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Contents

Editors Note	5
Fractions or kalāsavarṇa - Concepts in the Gaṇitasārasaṅgraha (G.S.S) of Mahāvira	Dr. P.M.Mini 7
Vrikshayurveda Literature- A Review	Dr. K.Murali 12
Existence Of Mind and its Function: Śrī Śankara's Perspective	Dr. V Vasanthakumari 23
Regional Peculiarities in Prakriyāsarvasva	Yamuna.K 30
Parāstotra - Edition and Study	Dr. J.P. Prajith 37
Alienation through Exile: A Critical Introspection into John Dos Passos' Nineteen Nineteen	Dr. Sanil T. Sunny 44
The Evolution of Indian Sculptural Art: Interaction with Western Styles and Development of Modernism	Dr. T.G Jyothilal 49
Scope of Sanskrit Studies in the Kerala Context	Dr.Shylaja S 55
Desamangalam Srikantha Variar - A Versatile Scholar	Dr.V.P.Udayakumar 67
A Comprehensive Review of Adharaneeya and Dharaneeya Vega	Dr. H.A.Anu, Dr. Haritha Chandran, Dr. Haroon Irshad, Dr. Leena P.Nair 72
A Significant Emphasis on Charakokta Chaturvidha Pariksha	Dr.Kesavan.V G, Dr.Haroon Irshad, Dr.Leena P.Nair, Dr. Haritha Chandran 84
Concept Of Manas- A Glimpse from Yoga Darsana	Dr. Anu Gopal, Dr. Haritha Chandran, Dr. Leena P Nair, Dr. Haroon Irshad 96
Women Life in Royal Harem- A Study Based on Nāṭyaśāstra And Mālavikāgnimitra	Dr. Ajitha T S 106
Effective Strategies For Implementing The Integrated Teacher Education Programme Under NEP- 2020	Prof. K.K. Harshkumar, Dr. Anand Rautmale 113
“Pancha Mahabhuta in Ayurveda: Understanding and Practical Applications”	Dr. Aswiny Sreekumar.T 121
“Dynamic Portrayals of Women in Amarushatak: Unravelling Love, Creation, Destruction, Submission, and Dominance”	Dr. Preeti R. Pujara 135
Literary Representation of the Ashtamudi Lake sketched through Poetic Imagery: An Exploration based on Selected Poems in Malayalam	Jayalekshmi J 145
Reviving Classical Narratives: Exploring the Cultural, Linguistic, and Literary Significance of Sanskrit Literature in Contemporary Contexts	Dr. Yeshpal, 155
Vedic Thought on Nakshatra Science	Dr. Kanta 172
Vedāntic Reflections in Kālidāsa's Literature: A Journey through Ancient Wisdom	Dr. K. K. Abdul Majeed 179
The Transformative Power of Yogic Meditation: Insights from the Isha Upanishad	Dev Prakash Gujela, Neha Gujela 188
Sanskrit: The Language of Innovation in Ancient Indian Knowledge Systems.	Abdul Rasheed K. 197
The Role of Vedānta as a Mediator between Science and Religion	Dr. Abdulla Sha R., Dr. Midhun P., 207

Concept of Guṇa in Bhagavad Gīta	Dr. Shyji K.K.	212
Pancatantram's perspective of accepting an 'hors de combat'	Kasthuri P. K.	217
Integral Yoga of Sri Aurobindo	Remya.S	223
The Historical Aspects Of 'Translation' (Anuvādam) - An Overview	Dr. Sajeesh C S	227
The Malayali Diaspora in the US: A close reading of Mira Jacob	Nirupama Suneetha	235
From Elancon To Kollam: The Transformation of A Port Cty	Gowri S Panicker	242
Influence of Nārayaṇīya on Kṛṣṇagīti	Dr Jayanisha K	255
Subverting Ableist Binaries: An Analysis of the Confluence of Disability Studies and Blue Humanities in Toni Crowther's From Wheelchair to Water	Sneha Jacob	263
Connecting the Concept of 'Avatar' to the Concept of Consciousness in Upanishads	Venugopalan P.M	269
Extraction of historicity from Sanskrit literature	Soorya A.P	281
चिन्सुखेन प्रतिपादितं अविद्यालक्षणम्	डॉ. सन्तोष सि. आर्	285
सामाजिकसमस्यापरिहारे भरतीयज्ञानपरम्परान्तर्गतस्य योगशास्त्रस्य स्थानम्	डा. श्रीजित् टि.जि	289
पतञ्जलिकालीनः लोकव्यवहारः-महाभाष्याधारेण एकमनुशीलनम्	डा.रूपा. वि	293
मानवीयमूल्यबोधोत्तरणे मूच्छकटिकम्	ड.मृत्युञ्जयमण्डलः परेशकैवर्त्यः	299
रघुवंशमहाकाव्ये रसतत्त्वसमीक्षणम्	काञ्चनवारिकः	304
नारीचैतन्योद्बोधे शङ्खनादः	डॉ टुम्पा जाना	308
आधुनिकसंस्कृतसाहित्ये गलज्जलिकायाः वैशिष्ट्यम्	सतीश चन्द्र दास	313
श्रीमच्छंकराचार्यकृतच्छान्दोग्योपनिषद्भाष्यस्य कतिपयशब्दवाक्यानां रूपवाक्यशब्दार्थतत्त्वनिरूपणम्	रणिता घोष	321
सदाचारो वेदाश्च ।	डा.अशोक कुमार एन्.के.	327
साम्प्रतिकसन्दर्भे अपरिग्रहः	डॉ. शुभमयपाहाडी	331
मनुसंहिता : 'ब्रह्मतत्त्व' विषयकम् एकं संक्षिप्तं मतम्	अमल कुमार कर	335
श्रीकाशीमठाधीशानां श्रीमत्सुधीन्द्रतीर्थानां स्तोत्रेषु छन्दांसि तथा सौन्दर्यम्	दिव्यश्री जगदीश पै बि. , & भास्कर वि भट्टः	339
सिद्धान्तग्रन्थेषु ब्राह्मणमानम्	डा. राघवेंद्रः	347
एतत्संज्ञेत्यत्र कः समासः	डा. गोपालकृष्णन् रघुः	352
मेघदूतस्य सांस्कृतिकमीमांसा	डा. सत्येन्दु शर्मा	356
जान्-म्यूर-प्रणीतस्य 'श्रीपौलचरित्रम्' इति महाकाव्यस्य संस्कृतालङ्कारशास्त्रदृष्ट्या समीक्षामिका विमृष्टिः	डा. सौम्यजित् सेनः	360
आधुनिकयुगे संस्कृतशिक्षा प्रसारार्थं विद्यासागरस्यावदानम्	डः तानिया-सिकदारः	369
तद्धितप्रत्ययेषु इत्संज्ञकवर्णाः ।	आतिरा. जि	372
अद्वैतसिद्धेः मङ्गलश्लोकस्य अप्रामाण्यशङ्कावारणम्	कार्तिक शर्मा के , ड. हरिकृष्ण शर्मा के.एन्	376
न्यायव्याकरणतन्त्रानुसंधे पदस्वरूपविवेचनम्	प्रणबेष् भट्टाचार्यः	381
पीयूषवर्षश्रीजयदेवाचार्य-श्रीकेशवमिश्रयोः मते शान्तरसविमर्शः	सत्येनशीटः	387
आलंकारिकदण्डिस्वीकृतः शब्दालङ्कारप्रपञ्चः	डॉ. शुभ्रजित् सेनः	393
लिधा एव पदशब्दस्य प्रवृत्तिः	डा. सुदीप-मण्डलः	400
About the journal		407

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A Significant Emphasis on Charakokta Chaturvidha Pariksha

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Abstract

Ayurveda places a significant emphasis on Chaturvidha Pariksha, consisting of four pramanas, for understanding and applying knowledge in medicine. The concept of Pariksha in Ayurveda involves thorough examination and assessment of an individual's health condition. This includes physical, mental, and emotional aspects to determine one's unique constitution, imbalances, and overall well-being. The four pramanas used in Ayurvedic Pariksha are Aptopadesha (authoritative instructions), Pratyaksha (sensory perception), Anumana (inference), and Yukti (logical reasoning). These pramanas are applied to diagnose diseases, select treatment, and understand the underlying causes of imbalances. Aptopadesha provides authoritative statements, Pratyaksha relies on sensory perception, Anumana involves inferential knowledge, and Yukti represents intellectual reasoning. These pramanas are fundamental to Ayurvedic diagnosis and treatment, emphasizing a scientific

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and systematic approach in the field of medicine, and Ayurvedic research methodology should be framed based on these four Pramanas.

Introduction

Ayurveda is an applied science related to medicine hence it gives more importance to the testing and confirmation of facts and concepts. After reviewing the literature, it is clear that sage physicians of Ayurveda valued the importance of scientific knowledge in every regard. Ayurveda has emphasized the importance, need, and application of examination. As a traditional and ancient science, it incorporates a few principles or dictums from its contemporary sciences such as 'Darshana'. The Darshana shastra are authoritative works of ancient Indian philosophy. Thus, the philosophical foundation of Ayurveda arose from many schools of thought such as Samkhya, Vaisheshika, Nyaya, etc. Pramana is one of the key contributions of Darshana incorporated into Ayurvedic writings. Pramanas are tools or procedures for acquiring information about a specific topic or phenomenon. Ayurveda accepts these pramanas in the name of pariksha with some modification and uses it as a method of examination for understanding the disease and acquiring true knowledge. The establishment of the reality of an object with the help of pramana is pariksha.

Concept of Pariksha in Ayurveda

The word 'pariksha' is derived from the root 'iksh' which means 'to view, to consider, or to examine', and 'Pari' means 'from all sides'. According to Sabdakalpadruma, 'परितः ईक्ष्यते', means observation from all directions (VS et al.).

According to Acharya Chakrapani, pariksha is 'परीक्ष्यते व्यवस्थाप्यते वस्तु स्वरूपमनयेति परीक्षा प्रमाणानि' i.e Through which 'vastu swarupam' (Understanding all characteristics of dravya or something) gets established is said as pariksha or pramana (Caraka and Cakrapānidatta, vol. 1, Sutrasthana. XI. 17).

In Ayurveda, pariksha refers to the examination or assessment of an individual's health condition. It includes a thorough assessment of various factors, including physical, mental, and emotional aspects,

in order to comprehend the individual's unique constitution, imbalances, and overall well-being. Pariksha techniques are used to diagnose diseases, determine the underlying causes of imbalances, and make personalized treatment recommendations.

नापरीक्षितमभिनविशेत् - Should not take anything without examining it (Caraka and Cakrapāṇidatta, vol. 1 VIII.27). While coming to the treatment aspect, रोगमादौ परीक्षेत ततोऽनन्तरमौषधम् । ततः कर्म भिषक् पश्चात्ज्ञानपूर्वं समाचरेत्॥ (Caraka and Cakrapāṇidatta, vol. 1, XX.20) i.e. a physician should first examine the patient and diagnose the disease, then he should examine the medicine and select the medicine. After acquiring complete knowledge of the disease and medicine only one should start the treatment. The purpose of this examination is to obtain knowledge regarding the line of treatment that should be adopted with a view to correcting morbidity.

Acharya Charaka has mentioned the concept of Chaturvidha pariksha in Sutrasthana, Tisreshaneeya Adhyaya. In Vimanasthana, Trividharogaviseshavijnaneeya chapter also describes the application of this pariksha in detail.

Table-1: Classification of Pariksha

Dvidha pariksha (Charaka)	Pratyaksha, Anumana
Trividha pariksha (Charaka, AH)	Aptopadesa, Pratyaksha, Anumana Darsana, Sparsana, Prasna
Chaturvidha pariksha (Charaka)	Aptopadeśa, Pratyakṣa, Anumana, Yukti
Ṣadvidha pariksha (Susruta)	Pancha jnanendriya evam Prasna pariksha
Aṣtasthāna pariksha (Y.R)	Naḍi, Mutraṃ, Malam, Jihva, Shabda, Sparsha, Drik, Akruṭi
D a s h a v i d h a pariksha (Charaka, AH)	Prakruti, Vikruti, Sara, Samhanana, Pramana, Satmya, Satwa, Ahara shakti, Vyayama shakti, Vaya. (Cha)

D v a d a s h a v i d h a pariksha	Dosha, Bsheshaja, Desha, Kala, Bala, Shareera, Sara, Ahara, Satmya, Satva, Prakruti, Vaya
---------------------------------------	---

An overview of Chaturvidha Pariksha

The concept of Chaturvidha pariksha is mentioned by Acharya Charaka in Sutrasthana, Tisreshaniya adhyaya. Here acharya explains that all the things in the universe can be divided into two i.e., Sat and Asat, these can be examined by *four means* or methods named *chaturvidha pariksha*, are Aptopadesha, Pratyaksha, Anumana, and Yukti. Charaka mentioned these pramanas for proving the existence of punarjanma and also the examination of sat and asat. Acharya Charaka only included Yukti as a separate pramana. In Vimanasthana of Charaka samhita a separate chapter called Trividharogavisheshavijnaneeya describes these pramanas. Here Charaka mentioned that ‘specific features of diseases can be determined in three ways by means of Aptopadesha (authoritative instruction), Pratyaksha (direct observation), and Anumana (inference)’ (Caraka and Cakrapāṇidatta, vol. 1, Vimanasthana. IV. 3). Yukti, the fourth pramana, is included under Anumana pramana however Yukti is very important in the context of treatment. it provides a practical approach to the rest of the pramana, enhancing their utility.

Aptopadesha (Authoritative instructions)

Aptopadesha means authoritative statement. It is verbal comprehension or testimony of knowledge. This testimony is an assertion by a trustworthy authority in the concerned field of knowledge termed as ‘Aapta’. Aapta is enlightened and knowledgeable individual, absolutely free from rajas and tamas (psychological doshas). Hence, they possess knowledge of the past, present, and future (trikala) and are known as Aapta. They are also known as Shishta (wise) and Vibuddha (enlightened) individuals. Their words are considered absolute truth without any doubt (Caraka and Cakrapāṇidatta, vol. 1, Sutrasthana. Vol1. Chapter 11. Verse 18-19). It is also known as “Shabda” (statement). It is the authentic source of literary knowledge or the primary source of information related to any subject. For those who have prior knowledge through आप्तवचनम् only two sources of examination are sufficient i.e., Pratyakṣa and

Anumana (Caraka and Cakrapāṇidatta, vol. 2, IV.5).

Aptopadesha can be applied in the examination and treatment of diseases, The following can be observed through the means of aptopadesha pramana

Table-2: Characteristic features of disease (Caraka and Cakrapāṇidatta, vol. 2, IV.6)

प्रकोपणम्	प्रकोपणं वायो रूक्षत्वादिहेतुः	Provoking Factors of disease Ex:- Rukshadi hetu leads to vata prakopa
योनि	योनिः वातादयः	Doshas involved in disease
उत्थानम्	उत्थानस्य उद्गमनादौ	Mode of manifestation of disease
आत्मानम्	आत्मा स्वभावः; यथा- रोहिण्यादारुणत्वं, सत्र्यासस्य शीघ्रोपक्रमणीयत्वादि	Nature of Disease; Ex: Darunatva of Rohini, Need for urgent treatment of Samnyasa.
अधिष्ठानम्	अधिष्ठानं शरीरमवयवा मनश्च	Location of disease (Sharira avayava &Manas)
वेदन	तोद, भेद	Type of pain
संस्थानम्	आकृति, स्वरूपम्	Clinical features
शब्दस्पर्शरूपरसगन्धम्	कपाल वर्ण	Association with specific sound, touch, colour etc
उपद्रवम्	तृष्णज्वरदाहादि in कुष्ठ	Complications of Disease
उदर्क	उदर्क उत्तरकालीनं फलं	Future complications
नामानम्	गृध्रसि, अवबाहुक	Naming the disease
योगं	Medications	Treatment Prescriptions of Disease

Pratyaksha Pramana

Pratyaksha pramana represents sensory perception. Here, the individual receives knowledge through the use of sense organs(Annambhaṭṭa 56). According to Ayurveda, it is the most basic and important instrument for disease diagnosis, prognosis, inference, conclusion, and treatment. Acharya Charaka has defined Pratyakṣa as vyakta (definite) and tadatva (immediate) knowledge arising from the conjugation of Atma, Indriya, Manas, and Artha (Caraka and Cakrapāṇidatta, vol. 1, Sutrasthana. Chapter XI. 20).

The physician gains knowledge about the status of the patient's condition and disease manifestation with the help of Pratyakṣa pramana through jnanendriyas except rasanendriya (Caraka and Cakrapāṇidatta, vol. 2, Vimanasthana. IV. 7). Based on these sense organs involved, Pratyakṣa jnana can be classified into five. (IV.7.).

Śrotrendriya Pratyakṣa (Auditory perception): Auditory perception is useful to understand pathology in various conditions through the medium of sound (shabda). The sounds like Antrakujana, Sandhisphutana, and Anguliparvana.

Sparshanendriya Pratyakṣa (Tactile Perception): Tactile perception is used to know about normal or pathological body characteristics such as heat/hotness (aushnya), coldness (shaitya), softness (mardava), hardness (kathinya), smoothness (shlakshna), and roughness (kharata).

Chakshurindriya Pratyakṣa (Visual perception): Through the medium of visual perception, the varna (complexion), samsthana (shape, location, appearance, form), pramana (size or measurements), chaaya (altered complexion), prakruti (normalcy), vikruti (abnormal characteristics), upachaya (good nourished built), apachaya (malnourished built) can be assessed.

Rasanendriya Pariksha: This examination is applicable for the purpose of organoleptic and taste threshold studies. In clinical practice, this can't be done by the physician himself. It is done indirectly either by interrogation or by inspection/inference.

Ex: मक्षिकोपसर्पणेन शरीरमाधुर्यं (Attraction of flies towards patient indicates excessive sweetness in the body). In this context, anumana pramana is applicable and not pratyakṣa.

अरुचि, आस्यवैरस्य (Impairment of taste) - Assessed through interrogation

Ghranendriya pratyakṣa (Olfactory perception): It helps to examine the normal and abnormal smell of body fluids or body odor.

Ex: Visram shareeragandha in prameha

Anumana Pramana

Anumana is a type of inferential knowledge. It refers to cognition that occurs after past information. It entails making assumptions or postulations regarding unknown or lesser-known facts based on prior knowledge of previously documented occurrences. As a result,

anumana gives information that is applicable to all time frames. Charaka defines, Anumana as a tool for obtaining knowledge preceded by pratyaksha pramana. It provides knowledge of the past, present, and future. For example, the presence of fire can be inferred from the appearance of smoke; the copulation in the past is inferred by witnessing pregnancy and predicting the future tree after examining the seed (Caraka and Cakrapāṇidatta, Vol1. Sutrasthana. XI. 21-22).

The objects known by pratyakṣa are very limited. Hence, it is necessary to understand the phenomena by Agama, Anumana, and Yukti (Caraka and Cakrapāṇidatta, Vol1. Sutrasthana. II. 7). The physician must use anumana, to determine the patient's prognosis and look up their past history. Assessment of various physiological entities like Agni (digestion), Bala (strength), Indriya shakti (sensorium), etc

Table.3: Clinical Application of Anumana Pramana (Caraka and Cakrapāṇidatta, Vol 2. Vimanasthana. IV. 8).

अग्निं जरणशक्त्या	Assessment of Agni by quality and quantity of food consumed and digested
बलं व्यायामशक्त्या	Assessment of physical strength by capacity to exercise
श्रोत्रादीनि शब्दाद्यर्थग्रहणेन	Functioning of the sense organs assessed by the clarity and accuracy of perception of their respective objects.
व्याधिं वेदनया	Assessment of disease by signs and symptoms
गूढलिङ्गं व्याधिमुपशयानुपशयाभ्यां	Assessed by the effectiveness of treatment in terms of relief or no relief/ aggravation.
दोषप्रमाणविशेषमपचारविशेषेण	Dosha pramana can be assessed by the level of consumption of provocative factors
आयुषः क्षयमरिष्टैः	Assessment of imminent death by the presence of Ariṣṭa lakshana or poor prognostic signs
सात्त्यं उपशयेन	Assessment of habituation by the level of wholesomeness

Yukti Pramana

'Yukti pramana' is included as a source of valid knowledge

in Ayurveda. It is considered as 4th pramana by Charaka. It is the intellectual perception that results from the examination of several causative elements. It denotes the logical reasoning and interpretation used to gain knowledge about any phenomenon. It is pure intellect information resulting from multifactorial, multidimensional thinking relevant in the past, present, and future (Caraka and Cakrapāṇidatta, Vol 1. Sutrasthana. XI.25). Yukti can also be defined as the preparation, application, and execution of information through the use of one's intellectual and reasoning ability.

Yukti is essential in identifying and analyzing the union of multiple factors in diagnosing, selecting medications, and treating patients. Treatment is successful when all of the components, such as Bhishak, Aushadham, Upasthata, and Rogi, work together. Yukti is one of the paradiguna, which is also known as Chikitsasidhyupaya, that are thought to be important for excellence and success in treatment. Yukti is defined as युक्तिश्च योजना या तु युज्यते|| which means it is important in rational and suitable treatment planning (Caraka and Cakrapāṇidatta, Vol 1. Sutrasthana. Vol1. XXVI. 29-30).

Discussion

Aaptopadesha

Aaptopadeśa is used in preventative, diagnostic, and treatment aspects.

Preventive aspects: The ultimate aim of Ayurveda is स्वस्थस्य स्वास्थ्यरक्षणं so, for this acharya explains different aspects of preventive medicine in terms of Dinacharya, R̥itucarya, Sadvritta, Vegadhāraṇa etc.

Diagnostic aspects: It provides accurate information on any disease in terms of its etiology, symptomatology, location, prognosis, and nomenclature. The Nidana Pancaka of many ailments mentioned in the text is the foundation of any particular disorder's understanding.

Treatment: Acharya mentioned different principles of treatment of various diseases like in the form of chikitsa sutra. The principles of shodhana, shamana, nidana parivarjana, and different medications and the principles of drug selection, drug identification,

and administration mentioned in the texts are the testimony of the application of aptopadeśa.

Aptodesha pramana is considered as a primary tool for research. It is the base for literary and conceptual research.

A thorough investigation of Aaptopdesha is beneficial in identifying the research problem

Aaptopadesha is the foundation of the literary and historical review. A researcher should review the pertinent literature in his or her field of study. Aaptopadesha can assist researchers in establishing the principles of the study and reaffirming them with his findings.

Acharya stated Vadamarga detailed in Rogabhishajiteeyadhyaya of Charaka Samhita, Vimana Sthana are aimed to perfect oneself in the skill of debate or discussion and the Siddhanta mentioned in 44 Vadamargas is demonstrated truth, established after multiple tests and reasoning. These can be compared to established theories.

Pratyaksha Pramana

The pratyaksha pramana is first-hand evidence. The significance of pratyaksha stems from the fact that it is the only method that is accepted by all philosophical schools. Though Ayurveda supports multiple sorts of knowledge methods, the excellence of pratyaksha stays intact. Darshana (observation), Sparshana (touching), and Prashna (asking different types of inquiries) are the three ways of patient examination mentioned in Ayurveda. The first two are directly based on Pratyaksha, and one can only interrogate the patient after directly seeing the signs that are present in the patient.

The acquisition of knowledge by direct observation or practical experiences is known as pratyaksha pramana. It is the basic data-collecting approach, in which the researcher notes the phenomena that he or she is experiencing at the time. This is an important part of several randomized controlled trials, case studies, and observational studies.

Anumana Pramana

Anumana is a tool for the assessment of imbalance of the dosha in terms of vruddhi (hyperfunctioning) and kshaya (hypo functioning), dhatu, mala, etc. Signs of a disease can be

observed by Pratyakṣa pramaṇa, but symptoms are assessed using the deliberation of Anumana pramaṇa. It also helps in predicting the prognosis, chance of survival of the patient and outcomes of the treatment in the future. Anumana helps in the assessment of subtle individual entities like agni, ojas, dhatu, dosha, mana, atma that cannot be directly perceived by sensorial faculties, but only by referring to their characteristics and functions.

The Anumana pramaṇa assists the researcher in establishing a cause-and-effect link by recognizing information in all three stages of time, namely the past, present, and future. It has a wide range of applications in research since it is concerned with the use of deductive, inductive, and analogical reasoning to analyze facts. Based on trikala three types of anumana explained by Acharya Chakrapani, are Poorvavat, Sheshavat, and Samanyatodrishta. This poorvavat presents Karanatkarya anumna, which is the anumna of the effect from the cause. This can be linked to a cohort or prospective study. Sheshavat is Karyatkaarana anumna is anumna of the cause from the effect, which can be linked to a case-control study (i.e., a retrospective study). Samanyatodrishta is anumna from the currently seen events, which can be associated using a cross-sectional study design (Time prevalence study). Anumana pramaṇa is also can be applied in writing research reports and can be correlated with pancavayava vakya which comes under parartha anumana and it is very important in the interpretation of results from the collected data after an analytical or experimental study.

Yukti Pramana

The Yukti is applied in different aspects of clinical practice

Preventive Aspects: The benefits of Trayopastambha (three pillars of life) i.e., ahara (dietary habits), nidra (sleeping habits), and bramhacharya (sexual life and moral conducts) largely depend upon one's intellect and conduct. The three types of bala (strength and vitality) includes a type of acquired form i.e. yuktikrita bala. This is achieved through dietetic and lifestyle measures.

Characteristic of Physician: Yuktignyata, or the ability to think logically and rationally, is an important physician characteristic.

It enables him to make the proper selection of drugs or treatment modalities to treat any disease successfully.

Selection of Drug: Nothing in the universe exists that has no medicinal or therapeutic value. After the explanation of mahakashaya (different classes of medicine), it is said that the drugs listed are exemplary, and physicians may utilize other herbs based on their own knowledge and logic.

Diagnosing: Yukti pramana is used to diagnose Anukta vyadhi (unknown ailments) or conditions that are not addressed in the books. It can also be used to diagnose new and evolving disease conditions by Understanding prakriti (illness type), adhishtana (disease occurrence and manifestation sites), and samutthana (etiological causes).

Yukti pramana combines Aaptopadesha, Pratyaksha, and Anumana pramana with logical and creative thinking to produce a productive result. Any research project begins with deriving previously gained knowledge via aaptopadesha pramana, perceiving available information via pratyaksha pramana, deriving logical inferences via anumana pramana, and analysing, interpreting, and presenting the findings via yukti pramana. Thus, it can assist in establishing the facts advanced by anumana pramana or inference.

There are different views regarding the number of pramanas. Some scholars opine that there is only one pramana, while others mentioned them in various numbers. In this way, total pramanas are mentioned as ten in number. As Ayurveda is an independent and unique science of medicine, it has some independent pramanas also. Aptopadesha, pratyaksha, and anumana are the common pramanas accepted by Sankhya, Yoga, Nyaya, and Ayurveda. Yukti was added as the fourth Pramana by Acharya Charaka, while Upamana was added by Susruta. So Acharya Charaka only accepted Yukti as a separate pramana and specifically mentioned these four pramanas as Chaturvidha pariksha. Abundant use of Yukti in the diagnosis and management of diseases can be seen in Ayurvedic classics. Yukti can be used to diagnose a condition that is otherwise difficult to

diagnose. The Yukti helps to correlate the information and to arrive at a solid conclusion.

Conclusion

In Ayurveda, more emphasis has been given to scientific knowledge based on verification and validation. Ayurveda has developed its own approach for fact-finding and applied it in the realm of medicine. The classics explain many ways of inspection and investigation for this purpose. These methods of evaluation were known as Pariksha. The concept of Chaturvidha pariksha is the base for all the examinations mentioned in Ayurveda. An able physician always proceeds with their treatment after proper examination. By this one will get the pratipatti jnana, i.e., the knowledge of the treatment, with which disorder to be eliminated¹⁸. Ayurvedic research methodology should be framed based on these four Pramanas. Examinations such as Roga Pariksha, Rogi Pariksha, and Aushadha Pariksha, which are required for successful disease diagnosis and treatment, are based entirely on these examinations. These Methods of examination are similar to those described in Philosophy as Pramana.

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